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CHALLENGES TO MAINTAIN QUALITY IN MANAGEMENT EDUCATION – AN INDIAN PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract:

The paper presents a conceptual framework in the context of growth of management education and major problems which hamper the quality of management education and what steps required to improve its quality. Quality Education is regarded as one that contributes to social, political, cultural and economic transformation of a country. In the last five years, the number of B-schools in India has tripled to about 4,500 amounting to as many as 3, 60,000. The students community in changing India not only want education in modern emerging fields but they want education, which is of quality. Moreover they do not want to deprive of opportunities because of their social or economical background. Management education then needs expansion and strengthening in its infrastructure and therefore greater in puts. It is struggle between maintaining the quality while satisfying the needs of masses.

Keywords: Management, Quality, Up gradation, Innovations, Total Quality Management, Systematic Issues, Emerging Issues.

INTRODUCTION

The term “quality” is a Latin word and it means “What Kind of”. Quality is a relative term meaning different things to different people. Some researchers believe that “quality is fitness for use or purpose” and other believe that “conformance to standard”, but in general it should satisfy customers needs, and continuously keeps on performing it’s functions as required by customers as per agreed upon standards (Murad & Rajesh, 2010). The term Total Quality Management (TQM) is a management philosophy, which puts systems and processes in place to meet and exceed the expectations of customers (Rana, 2009). Managing the quality in Higher Education (HE) is very important and challenging and it is not like Industrial products that, once they are finish, take them or leave them; like them or dislike them; accept

them or reject them. Higher education is not a product in industrial sense rather it is a “service”. Graduates here are not a finish product but unfortunately understood as a finish product. Higher education is a service-oriented and goal-oriented and no doubt seen relatively from different cultural point of views (Becket & Brookes, 2008) (Pour & Yeshodhara, 2009).

Management education is one of the latest discipline to be added on the academic map of India. In the early 20th century, the first MBA program in management was launched by Dartmouth College followed by Harvard Business School in the United States later in 1960 in Europe. In 1961, the Government of India established IIM Calcutta on November 14, IIM Ahmedabad on December 11, Bangalore in 1971 and Lucknow in 1974 and in the late 1990s at Indore and Calicut. The flagship management education programme, MBA, is widely popular as it offers quick gateway to the riches and to the top echelon of corporate world.

The landscape of management education has undergone considerable change over the years. In the initial days the demand for management education had to be created and the institutions had to invest in exploratory marketing. During the 60s, 70s, and 80s though the institutions gave some weightage to students with work experience in their admission criteria most students did not have prior work experience. This trend started changing with the realization among executives working in professionally managed companies that their professional growth in their organizations could be facilitated by a management degree or diploma from a good institution. The 90s saw a significant increase in students with prior experience, which has continued since then.

The purpose of management education has been to enable business organisation to apply knowledge to improve organisational efficiency and effectiveness. Management education gives a holistic picture to the students about how to manage the four ‘M’s of any organization i.e. money, material, man and machine to focus on cost and quality, productivity, mass customization, project management, leadership has directly contributed to generation of wealth in business organisation.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Quality higher education and training is crucial for economies that want to move up the value chain beyond simple production processes and products. The report of World Economic Forum ranked 8th position of management education in India in 2007. By 2008, it came down to 12th position. 2009 saw more decline in the ranking, in 2011 it is in 23rd position. World Economic Forum Global Competitiveness Report 2013-2014 had ranked 101, This trend has to be arrested, and therefore providing quality education has become crucial.

OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

1. To study the evolution of management education in India.
2. To study the development & present scenario of management education in India..
3. To study the challenges of quality of management education in India.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Shubhendu (2013) has pointed out a part from 20 Business Schools like IIMS, merely 10% of graduates from other business schools are having corporate employability to get best placement and packages. Further there is a need of internationalize the approach to equip students to become a global manager. The key ingredient of a world class B-School is the faculty commitment towards research, teaching excellence and professional approach to understand the requirement for quality education. There is also need of financial resources to equip institution, faculty and students to create a global midset with management & leadership capabilities on a world wide scale (Saha, 2011).

Today's organisation faces enormous pressures from diverse stakeholders of the business environment along with the fast expanding domains of knowledge. Immediate requirement to shape the management education by introspecting on innovative methodologies of teaching and research in accordance with the global changes to improve competitiveness (John & Panchanatham, 2011). There is the need to fill the gap between theory and its practical aspects through industrial interaction so that the student can be exposed to real problem and exposure of industry. The education should be more practical oriented and industry focus to shape the management education in accordance with the global changes to improve competitiveness with the total quality management. The education should be as per the demand of managers for international business (Chaudhary, 2011). The organisation has to adopt innovative methods and practice to respond speed and diversity of globalization challenges (Patil, 2012).

PRESENT SCENARIO OF MANAGEMENT EDUCATION

In the last two decades, the growth of management education in India has been phenomenal. MBA and PGDM education currently is available through residential, fulltime and distance education mode. In addition to these AICTE approved programs, there are large number of foreign university which offers management education in the country, either independently or as a joint venture with Indian B-Schools.

According to annual report (2009-2010), published by Ministry of Human Resource Development, there were 20 Universities and 500 Colleges at the time of independence. At present, there are 533 Universities and university-level institutions (as on 31.12.2010) 257 State Universities, 41 Central Universities, 130 Deemed Universities, 39 institutions of national importance established under Acts of Parliament five Institutions established under various State legislations and 61 private universities. There are 25,951 colleges in 2009 of which, 7,178 are recognized under 2(f) and 5,936 colleges recognized under section 2(f) and declared fit to receive grants under section 12(B) of the UGC Act, 1956.

Table 1: Growth of Intake & AICTE Approved Management Institutions in Eight Years

Year	No. of Institution	Percentage Increase
2005-06	1052	---
2006-07	1132	7.60
2007-08	1149	1.50
2008-09	1523	32.55
2009-10	1940	27.38
2010-11	5.44	16.60
2011-12	2.73	
2012-13	2450	

Table (1) shown above shows growth of AICTE approved technical institutes in last eight years. In 2008-2009 the number institutes increased at highest around 33%.

Table 2: Growth of Intake in Management Institutions in Last Eight Years

Year	Intake	Percentage Increase
2005-06	80464	---
2006-07	94704	17.70
2007-08	121867	28.68
2008-09	149555	22.72
2009-10	179561	20.06
2010-11	277811	54.72
2011-12	352571	26.91
2012-13	385008	9.20

Table (2) shown above shows growth of intake of students in last eight years. In 2010-201 the intake of students has increased at exceptional rate, thus can be called the golden year for the institutes in respect of intake of students.

Employability and Management Education

The growing demand for MBA graduates has led to a rapid growth of B-schools, in every corner of the country. Although this mushrooming has taken care of the quantity issue, the quality of this talent is questionable. The institution on the one hand does not have proper infrastructure facilities to provide environment for learning and other the quality of faculty recruited for these management students is in question. One of the major concerns is also the student's attitude and approach towards learning and practical knowledge. A recent study by ASSOCHAM found out that a meager 10% of the B-school graduates are actually employable despite the demand.

CHALLENGES

Though there have been a number of committees that suggested improvements in management education, there have been no significant changes in management education. Most of the institution does not promote research, development of faculties, lack in facilities like faculty strength, library, and computer facilities.

1. **Quality Faculty:** The establishment of AICTE resulted in the sanctioning of a large number of B-Schools. While giving sanctions to a large number of institutions, AICTE was unable to create adequate machinery for the development and training of faculty to teach in management courses with an applied bias.
2. **Developing Material Relevant to the Indian Context.** There is an increasing awareness that many of the ideas and concepts that have been effective in the countries of their origin have been less effective in India. While many industrialized countries have tested and adopted management practices that are in perfect harmony with their culture and tradition, India is yet to do this exercise through systematic research and study.
3. **Governance and Accountability:** Most of the private B-Schools in India offering Post Graduate Diploma in Management are managed by charitable trusts or educational societies. In case of charitable trusts, the trustees are generally from the same family having absolute powers to manage the affairs of the institutions. The trustees hold the office for the whole life and hence cannot be removed for their indulgences or mis-governance or incompetence.
4. **Quality of Education.** Unfortunately, most of the B-schools have thrived on marketing gimmicks and advertising budget rather than intellectual endeavours. AICTE has given full autonomy to the B-Schools vis-à-vis curriculum development, assessment of students, conduct of examination, recruitment of faculty, tuition fee etc. However, there are no checks and balances on these matters. While the AICTE ensures compliance regarding infrastructure, library and laboratory facilities and student-faculty ratio, it overlooks the indicators of quality education.
5. **Commercialization.** As world economy has faltered, colleges and universities have been forced to adopt strategies for increasing revenues and decreasing cost. The strong growth of private and for profit institutions around the world has attracted a great deal of attention. Governments have admitted that they cannot provide places for all the qualified in their countries and this created legislation and policies which encourage private money flow into their countries for building new universities. Education itself has become an industry for international business.

CONCLUSION

The educational culture of the 21st century requires new packages and a fresh approach in tune with global futuristic trends in management education. The inappropriate infrastructure facilities, lack of research, engaging part time faculty, recruiting inexperienced candidate had worsen the position of management education. There is a need to develop a proper mechanism where in fair and transparent 360o evaluation of the institutions can be done to promote quality education. Further there is a need to develop interaction and strong relationship with industry through teaching, research, student placements, problem solving and case study preparation for developing liaison with industry. Reconstruction of management education has to recognize that managers need to attend to interpersonal relations, communication, conflicts, feelings, politics and the like. This brings us to the issue that there is a need for managers to connect to a wider set of public duties than that of corporate performance through a liberal education.

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